

Route of Opportunities

Roadmap for comprehensive support for people with vision or hearing loss and accompanying combat injuries

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Introduction to the Roadmap

The war has caused an unprecedented rise in the number of people with sensory impairments resulting from combat injuries. Loss of sight and/or hearing, particularly when combined with other combat injuries, is among the most disorienting and difficult-to-recover-from injuries, as it requires long-term, comprehensive rehabilitation covering medical, psychological, educational, vocational and social aspects.

For the individual, a sensory injury is not merely a functional limitation. It often triggers an identity crisis, reduces motivation, intensifies feelings of worthlessness and creates a high risk of social isolation. The recovery process affects not only the person undergoing rehabilitation but the whole family: in the first few months, confusion, fear, a sense of helplessness and the constant question «what is the right thing to do and how can we avoid causing harm?» become the norm.

Expert discussions and an analysis of practice have shown that in the first days and weeks following a trauma, people most commonly experience disorientation, a loss of autonomy and control, emotional instability, avoidance of social interaction, and a fear of movement or activity (kinesiophobia); amongst military personnel, apathy and a sense of meaninglessness are also frequently observed.

At the same time, there are systemic barriers to the provision of support: the absence of a single standardised approach to support at all stages; fragmentation between services (medical, psychological, social and educational-vocational components operate without a shared logic); unclear criteria for transition between stages; loss of information when a person moves between institutions; insufficient preparation of the family and adaptation of the home environment; scattered data and the inability to see a complete picture of progress. A separate gap is the lack of tools and practices for assessing the educational and vocational potential and skills necessary for a return to productive activity.

The consequences of such a «disconnected» system are very practical and painful: regression (loss of acquired skills), prolonged rehabilitation periods due to chaotic and duplicated interventions, inefficient use of resources, secondary traumatisation and social isolation, as well as a low rate of return to productive activity despite the individual's potential.

The key challenge is the lack of a common language among all those involved in the process. When everyone describes a person's condition and needs «in their own language» (using different terms, criteria and priorities), decisions become out of sync, important information is lost during transitions between institutions, and the family receives conflicting signals and is left alone to decide on the next steps.

This is precisely why the proposed approach centres on the Roadmap «Route of Opportunities» as a common language for coordination, which:

- establishes a consistent framework for the stages from injury to the restoration of quality of life, autonomy and return to activity;
- establishes agreed criteria for transitions between stages to minimise subjectivity in decision-making and «gaps» in support;
- standardises basic definitions of conditions and indicators of change so that specialists, families and managers share a common understanding of progress and risks;
- defines a minimum set of information to be shared between institutions and teams (via a «Patient Rehabilitation Profile»), reducing data loss and duplication of interventions;
- helps to align the roles and responsibilities of those involved in the process – from the family to inter-agency coordination at the community and state levels.

The Roadmap is implemented through three interlinked components: the individual rehabilitation pathway, the Patient Rehabilitation Profile (to record the starting point, changes and key indicators), and Recommendations for professionals and families, which ensure a shared understanding of the appropriate actions at each stage. The approach is based on international practices in the rehabilitation and support of veterans and is aligned with national priorities for the development of the rehabilitation system and veteran services.

In this sense, the guide serves as a practical vehicle for the Roadmap's common language: it helps to utilize the stages, transition criteria and «Patient Rehabilitation Profile» to coordinate decisions within the team, the family and the support system.

Individual rehabilitation route: concept and structure

An **individualised route** is a standardised logic for a rehabilitatee to go through key stages, from acute trauma to restoring quality of life, linked to the five components of the person-centred model.

1. General logic (framework)

Each person goes through different stages, but standards provide a unified system of guidelines that helps avoid chaos.

The route consists of six basic stages:

1. Acute stage: stabilisation and safety
2. Initial adaptation: reducing shock and anxiety
3. Formation of autonomy and basic skills
4. Psychological and identity recovery
5. Educational and professional rehabilitation
6. Long-term integration and quality of life

This is a **universal standard**, and within it there are individual trajectories.

2. Details of the stages (*duration is approximate*)

Stage 1. Stabilisation and safety (0–14 days)

Objectives:

- physical and psychological safety
- control of shock, anxiety, disorientation
- risk minimisation

Criteria for moving on:

- basic orientation
- reduction of acute anxiety
- capacity for minimal interaction

Stage 2. Initial adaptation (2–6 weeks)

Goals:

- stabilisation of functional status
- basic mobility and self-care skills
- building trust in the team
- reducing dependence on external assistance

Criteria for moving on:

- reducing fear of movement
- ability to follow simple instructions
- stability of emotional reactions

Stage 3. Basic autonomy (6–12 weeks)

Goals:

- development of mobility
- orientation in the environment
- development of independence in daily activities
- stabilisation of rhythms (sleep, activity)

Criteria for moving on:

- ability to move independently in familiar surroundings

- performance of everyday activities
- readiness for cognitive load

Stage 4. Identity and psychological recovery (2–6 months)

Goals:

- forming a new identity after trauma
- restoring motivation and initiative
- working with frustration, loss, and role changes

Criteria for moving on:

- ability to set personal/everyday goals
- emotional regulation
- interest in learning or activities

Stage 5. Educational and professional stage (3–12 months)

Goals:

- return to education/retraining
- professional assessment and planning
- environmental adaptations (tactile, auditory, digital)

Criteria for moving on:

- stable independent mobility skills
- sufficient psychological stability
- willingness to take responsibility

Stage 6. Long-term integration (from 12 months)

Goals:

- social inclusion
- stable life activities
- professional independence
- quality of life (subjective and objective)

Transition (completion of the route):

- independence in key areas of life
- stable social roles
- sustainable adaptation mechanisms

3. Linking the route to the Status Passport

At each stage, the following are recorded:

- **functional status according to 5 components**
- **risks and signs of regression**
- **micro-goals for 2–6 weeks**
- **level of autonomy**
- **recommendations for the team and family**

The passport becomes **a tool for navigating the route.**

4. Standardised «transition points» between stages

For systematic work, it is important to define standardised transition criteria:

Psychological: stabilisation of emotional reactions, ability to make contact

Functional: minimum set of self-care skills

Sensory: ability to navigate a safe space

Communicative: accessibility of communication channels

Motivational: initiative, readiness to act

This allows for the **unification of support team decisions** and avoids subjectivity.

5. IF-THEN model (*for making decisions about continuing along the route*)

The route can operate according to the following logic:

- **IF** the level of anxiety is high → **THEN** return to stabilisation interventions
- **IF** autonomy increases → **THEN** focus on orientation and mobility
- **IF** initiative appears → **THEN** inclusion in educational and professional routes
- **IF** social interaction is limited → **THEN** work with accessible communication

This ensures **adaptability and predictability**.

Why do the system and experts need this route?

- It ensures standardised operating logic.
- It allows for the integration of different institutions.
- It provides common criteria for all teams.
- It unifies performance evaluation.
- It ensures transparency and predictability for the rehabilitant.
- It forms the basis for the **Roadmap and Rehabilitation Profile**.

DETAILED MODEL OF THE TOOL «Patient Rehabilitation Profile»

1. Logic and rationale behind the composition of parameters

The «Patient Rehabilitation Profile» tool is based on the logic of a holistic, **person-centred model of recovery**, which identifies five components:

- **Basic psychological stability and sense of security**
- **Autonomy and functional mobility**
- **Self-awareness, identity and motivation**
- **Social interaction and social integration**
- **Quality of life and long-term resilience**

This composition is based on **three key arguments**:

Argument 1. Functional recovery model (WHO ICF)

International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF, WHO):

- proposes viewing a person through bodily functions, activity, participation in life, personal factors, and environmental conditions;
- emphasises the need for a meaningful assessment of changes, not just medical parameters;
- supports a comprehensive approach to disability and rehabilitation.

Our 5 components integrate the key domains of the ICF:

- mental functions → Components 1 and 3
- motor skills and activity → Component 2
- participation in life → Component 4
- personal factors + quality of life → Component 5

Argument 2. The logic of the rehabilitation path (dynamic model)

The path to recovery for people with vision loss, hearing loss, combined sensory impairments (deafblindness), and related combat injuries is not linear, but rather a dynamic process that passes through the same substantive areas of change:

1. First, the person must regain a sense of security and orientation.
2. Next, they must regain control over their body and actions.
3. Then, they must achieve self-awareness and see their prospects.
4. Next, they must become involved in society.
5. And finally, they must find stability and quality of life.

These changes are not strictly tied to the stages of the route – they can occur in parallel, in waves, with regressions and breakthroughs.

Therefore, it is logical to group the parameters according to the content of the person's condition, rather than according to the stages of the route.

Argument 3. Psychological mechanisms of adaptation after trauma

Psychological science describes adaptation after loss of function (sensory or physical) as going through:

1. Shock – disorientation
2. Search for control – functional adaptation
3. Reinterpretation of oneself – formation of a new identity

4. Restoration of social roles
5. Stabilisation, integration, new level of quality of life

This **fully corresponds to the 5 components of the tool**, with the difference that we make them measurable.

COMPONENT 1. BASIC PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY AND SENSE OF SECURITY

What we measure:

- level of anxiety/panic
- internal sense of physical and psychological security
- orientation in one's condition
- ability to perceive information
- primary sense of control

Example statements:

1. I feel safe here and now.
2. I understand what is happening to me.
3. I can perceive and remember information.
4. My anxiety prevents me from acting. (reverse code)
5. I feel that I can cope with my situation.

No	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score (0–4)	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
1.1	Sense of security	«I feel safe here and now»			
1.2	Orientation in the state	«I understand what is happening to me»			
1.3	Ability to perceive information	«I can listen, understand and remember»			
1.4	Level of anxiety	«My anxiety prevents me from acting» (reverse statement)			
1.5	Basic control	«I feel at least a little bit like I can handle this»			

Why is this important? Because without it, it is impossible to orient oneself in information or develop autonomy. This is a fundamental condition for any subsequent action.

What we measure: anxiety, orientation and basic sense of control.

Interpretation: low values → the person is not ready for active rehabilitation.

Positive dynamics: the first sign that the person is «coming back to themselves».

COMPONENT 2. AUTONOMY AND FUNCTIONAL MOBILITY

What we measure:

- fear of movement
- self-care skills
- ability to move around (with a cane, with support, independently)
- body awareness
- basic control over actions and situations

Example statements:

1. I am afraid to move independently. (reverse code)
2. I can perform daily activities independently.
3. I move confidently in familiar spaces.
4. I understand my body in new conditions.
5. I can plan my movements and actions.

No	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
2.1	Fear of movement	«I am afraid to move on my own» (reverse statement)			
2.2	Self-care skills	«I can perform basic daily activities independently»			
2.3	Mobility	«I move confidently in familiar spaces»			
2.4	Body image	«I understand my body in new conditions»			
2.5	Control of movements and actions	«I can plan my movements and actions»			

Why is this important? Autonomy is a key indicator of functional rehabilitation. Without it, there can be no return to normal life.

What we measure: fear of movement, self-care skills, mobility, body awareness

Interpretation: an increase in points indicates real progress along the route.

This is a central block for people with vision/hearing loss.

COMPONENT 3. SELF-AWARENESS, IDENTITY, MOTIVATION

What we measure:

- self-image in a new situation
- professional vision
- self-efficacy
- intrinsic motivation to act
- reduction of feelings of hopelessness

Example statements:

1. I see opportunities for my professional future.

2. I feel that I have valuable skills.
3. I want to learn or try new activities.
4. The future seems hopeless to me. (reverse code)
5. I feel my value and ability to develop.

No	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
3.1	The image of a professional future	«I have at least a rough idea of what I could do»			
3.2	Self-efficacy	«I feel that I have valuable skills»			
3.3	Motivation for action	«I want to learn/try new things»			
3.4	Fear of the future	«The future scares me» (reverse statement)			
3.5	Self-esteem and self-worth	«I feel my importance and ability to develop»			

Why is this important? After trauma, a new identity is formed – without this, it is impossible to have a purpose in life.

What we measure: vision of the future, motivation, self-belief.

Interpretation: stable growth in this block allows for transition to professional rehabilitation.

COMPONENT 4. SOCIAL INTERACTION AND INTEGRATION

What we measure:

- social confidence
- interaction with people
- ability to fulfill social roles
- social connectivity and participation
- readiness for team/community integration

Example statements:

1. I feel comfortable interacting with other people.
2. I have people with whom I communicate regularly.
3. I feel like part of a community/family/group.
4. I can handle some social affairs on my own.
5. I am ready to participate in community life.

No	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
4.1	Social confidence	«I feel more comfortable engaging with others than I did before»			

№	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
4.2	Membership / participation	«I feel like I'm part of a group/community»			
4.3	Social contacts	«I have people with whom I communicate regularly»			
4.4	Independence in social actions	«I can handle some social affairs on my own»			
4.5	Collaborative readiness	«I am ready to be part of a team or group»			

Why is this important? Because recovery without social inclusion is only half the route.

What we measure: connectivity, participation, social agency and confidence.

Interpretation: this component is critically important in the transition period to employment.

COMPONENT 5. QUALITY OF LIFE, RESILIENCE AND LONG-TERM ADAPTATION

What we measure:

- subjective assessment of quality of life
- ability to overcome difficulties
- ability to plan
- participation in family or community life
- emotional stability

Example statements:

1. Overall, I am satisfied with my life right now.
2. I know how to cope with difficult situations.
3. I can plan for the future.
4. My emotional state is stable throughout the day/week.
5. I am active in the life of my family or community.

№	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
5.1	Subjective quality of life	«Overall, I am satisfied with my life right now»			
5.2	Strategies for overcoming	«I have ways of coping with difficulties»			
5.3	Planning for the future	«I can plan ahead and set goals»			

No	Indicator	Description / Statement	Starting score	Post-stage assessment	Post-stage assessment
5.4	Emotional stability	«My emotional state has been relatively stable throughout the week»			
5.5	Social activity	«I participate in the life of my family or community»			

Why is this important? This is the resulting component that allows us to understand whether a person has truly «returned to life» or is simply «functioning»

What we measure: life satisfaction, resilience, planning and participation.

Interpretation: high values = successful rehabilitation; low values = need for further support.

FINAL BLOCK OF ASSESSMENT

Component	Starting score	Score after stage 1	Score after stage 2	Score after stage 3	Score after stage 4
1. Stability and security					
2. Autonomy and mobility					
3. Identity and motivation					
4. Social interaction					
5. Quality of life					

3. Interpreting the Results: How to Read and Understand Them?

Two models are available – basic and advanced.

✓ SIMPLIFIED INTERPRETATION (for practitioners)

Component scores:

0–1: critical level → the individual is not ready for the next stages

2: low level → intensive work is required

3: medium level → transition to the next stage is possible

4: high level → good progress, readiness to move forward

This is easy to explain to both the individual and the team.

✓ EXTENDED INTERPRETATION (for specialists, analysts, roadmaps)

1. BASELINE SCORES

→ form **the initial state profile**. For example: high scores in autonomy, low scores in stability = risk of emotional breakdown.

2. DYNAMICS

→ the main criterion for success. Positive dynamics in 3 out of 5 components = successful stage.

3. GAPS (Discrepancies)

→ if one component is «lagging behind», the route needs to be adjusted. For example: a person is autonomous but lacks social confidence → high risk of failure in employment.

4. PROFILES FOR DIFFERENT TYPES OF TRAUMA

the tool allows you to see:

- deafblind profile
- profile heavy PTSD
- profile with cognitive impairment
- amputee + sensory loss

This enables the customization of the roadmap to fit the specific type of rehabilitee.

REGULATORY AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS FOR THE STRUCTURE OF THE TOOL «Patient Rehabilitation Profile»

(international standards, protocols, recommendations)

1. International documents defining rehabilitation standards

1.1. International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) World Health Organization (WHO), 2001

- Defines domains of functioning: **psychological functions, activity, participation, personal factors, environment.**
- The proposed structure of indicators («5 components») is an integration of key ICF domains.
- It allows us to form **a comprehensive profile of a person's functioning, which is the goal of our tool.**

Justification: The components «psychological stability», «autonomy», «social interaction», and «quality of life» directly reflect the areas of functioning that, according to the ICF, determine a person's level of functioning after trauma.

1.2. «WHO Rehabilitation 2030: A Call for Action» (World Health Organisation, 2017)

Key provisions:

- rehabilitation should be person-centred,
- assessment should include functional, psychological and social parameters,
- dynamic assessment (not one-off) is mandatory,
- rehabilitation should include medical, psychosocial and vocational interventions.

Justification: our tool includes precisely these parameters: from emotional stability to autonomy, participation and quality of life; and provides for regular reassessment, which fully complies with WHO requirements.

1.3. «Guidelines on the Provision of Assistive Products» (WHO, 2022)

Indicates the need to:

- assess functional capabilities,
- determine the level of autonomy,
- take into account the personal goals of the rehabilitant,
- assess the context of the social environment.

Justification: components 2 (autonomy) and 4 (social integration) fully comply with these recommendations.

1.4. Rehabilitation Interventions Package (WHO, 2020)

Develops standardised intervention models, including:

- psychological,
- sensory,
- mobility,
- social.

Justification: RIP is based on the principle of assessing abilities and barriers, not just the disease. Our tool works on the same logic.

2. European standards and institutional recommendations

2.1. The European Disability Rights Strategy 2021–2030

- emphasises the importance of independence,
- participation in public life,
- access to education and employment.

Justification: components 2, 3, 4 and 5 directly correspond to the requirements of this strategy.

2.2. European Quality Framework for Social Services (2010)

- the key quality parameters are: participation, self-determination, safety, effectiveness of support,
- emphasising the need to assess personal development.

Justification: this directly corresponds to components 1 (safety), 4 (social interaction) and 5 (resilience and quality of life).

2.3. Nordic Welfare Centre standards for deafblind people (2015–2019)

- recommendations for working with people with dual sensory impairments,
- including requirements for assessment of communication, mobility, social participation and psychological state.

Justification: our five components cover all domains required by these standards.

3. Recommendations and protocols for the rehabilitation of military personnel and individuals with combat injuries

3.1. NATO Centre of Excellence for Military Medicine – Rehabilitation Guidelines (2018–2022)

- Systematic assessment
- Psychophysiological stability
- Autonomy and mobility
- Social adaptation of veterans
- Quality of life as the ultimate criterion

Justification: our tool is fully consistent with military rehabilitation models.

3.2. VA Polytrauma System of Care (US Department of Veterans Affairs)

Model for individuals with:

- explosive injuries,
- combined sensory impairments,
- cognitive impairments.

The main assessment parameters include:

- emotional functions,
- independence,
- communication,
- social participation,

- quality of life.

Justification: our system of indicators corresponds to this model almost completely.

4. Psychological and clinical models of adaptation after loss of function

4.1. Lindemann's model – major recovery after crisis

Describes the sequence of transition from shock → to adaptation → to constructive living.

4.2. Moos–Shaeffer model of post-traumatic adaptation

Includes:

- emotional state,
- coping strategies,
- social resources,
- confidence and motivation.

4.3. International concepts of grief & loss in sensory impairment

(Kübler-Ross model + modern adaptations for sensory loss)

Justification: components 1–5 reflect all key psychological mechanisms of adaptation.

5. Summary of regulatory justification

The proposed structure of indicators in the «Patient Rehabilitation Profile»

- is **confirmed by WHO, ICF, and Rehabilitation 2030 standards,**
- corresponds to European approaches to **independence, participation, and integration,**
- is fully consistent with recommendations for the rehabilitation of **military personnel and individuals with sensory impairments,**
- reflects psychological models of **adaptation after loss of function,**
- provides a **universal, interdisciplinary and inter-stage assessment format,**
- allows the formation of a **dynamic profile of an individual's recovery,** as required by modern international approaches.

Thus, the structure of the tool is methodologically sound, evidence-based, internationally valid and adapted to the Ukrainian context.

AFTERWORD

The materials in the Guide are the result of the «Route of Opportunities» online laboratory held in December 2025 and a preliminary expert survey. The survey involved 31 experts, including 5 combatants with relevant injuries; typical psycho-emotional states at different stages, indicators of positive change, criteria for increased autonomy, risks of regression and methods for recognising them were recorded.

The online laboratory took the form of structured work by expert groups, conducted via online meetings with the outcomes recorded in real time.

The Roadmap is a common language for everyone involved in the rehabilitation of people with sensory impairments resulting from combat injuries. It is not intended to replace professional methodologies, but rather to harmonise the logic of interaction, make the transitions between stages visible, and minimise information loss at critical points along the route.

The key participants in this process are:

- the person with trauma and their family – to help navigate the process, understand the stages, risks and appropriate support measures without taking on the role of professionals;
- specialists from the multidisciplinary team – to agree on objectives, shared indicators of change and transition criteria, as well as to prevent regression;
- civil society organisations and partner initiatives – to integrate support programmes into the pathway, provide accompaniment and advocacy, and establish sustainable mechanisms for accessing services within the community;
- civil servants and local government officials – for inter-agency coordination, planning of services and resources, and evaluating effectiveness at the community/regional level.

All these groups view recovery from different perspectives, but the Roadmap enables them to act in a coordinated manner – through shared definitions, criteria and a sequence of decisions.

The common language of the Roadmap enables:

- agreement on the stages and objectives of the support process, so that everyone understands «where we are now» and «what the next step is»;
- standardise the criteria for transitions between stages, reducing the risk of erroneous «too early/too late» decisions;
- maintain continuity of support when changing institutions and teams thanks to a minimal handover package;
- identify risks of regression in a timely manner and respond before a «setback» in skills or emotional state occurs;

- enhance individual autonomy and reduce dependence on the environment through predictable support logic;
- support management and planning: link needs at each stage to services, resources and performance indicators.